

GENERAL SUM FORMULA FOR BI-PERIODIC FIBONACCI AND LUCAS NUMBERS

Elif Tan

Department of Mathematics, Ankara University, Ankara, Turkey
etan@ankara.edu.tr

Received: 9/5/16, Revised: 6/10/17, Accepted: 9/27/17, Published: 10/6/17

Abstract

In this paper, we give a general sum formula for the bi-periodic Fibonacci and Lucas numbers. Also, we express the general sum formula of the bi-periodic Lucas numbers in terms of the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers.

1. Introduction

The bi-periodic Fibonacci sequence $\{q_n\}$ is defined by Edson and Yayenie [2] as:

$$q_n = \begin{cases} aq_{n-1} + q_{n-2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ bq_{n-1} + q_{n-2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}, \quad n \geq 2 \quad (1)$$

with initial values $q_0 = 0$, $q_1 = 1$ and a, b are nonzero numbers. Its associative sequence, the bi-periodic Lucas sequence $\{p_n\}$, is defined by Bilgici [1] as:

$$p_n = \begin{cases} bp_{n-1} + p_{n-2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is even} \\ ap_{n-1} + p_{n-2}, & \text{if } n \text{ is odd} \end{cases}, \quad n \geq 2 \quad (2)$$

with the initial conditions $p_0 = 2$ and $p_1 = a$. These sequences can be seen as a generalization of the Fibonacci and Lucas sequences. If we take $a = b = 1$ in $\{q_n\}$, we get the classical Fibonacci sequence, and if we take $a = b = 1$ in $\{p_n\}$, we get the classical Lucas sequence.

Also, $\{q_n\}$ and $\{p_n\}$ both satisfy the following recurrence relation:

$$f_n = (ab + 2)f_{n-2} - f_{n-4}, \quad n \geq 4. \quad (3)$$

The Binet formulas of the sequences $\{q_n\}$ and $\{p_n\}$ are given by

$$q_n = \frac{a^{\xi(n+1)}}{(ab)^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}} \left(\frac{\alpha^n - \beta^n}{\alpha - \beta} \right) \quad (4)$$

and

$$p_n = \frac{a^{\xi(n)}}{(ab)^{\lfloor \frac{n+1}{2} \rfloor}} (\alpha^n + \beta^n) \tag{5}$$

respectively, where $\alpha = \frac{ab + \sqrt{a^2b^2 + 4ab}}{2}$ and $\beta = \frac{ab - \sqrt{a^2b^2 + 4ab}}{2}$ that is, α and β are the roots of the polynomial $x^2 - abx - ab$ and $\xi(n) = n - 2 \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ is the parity function, i.e., $\xi(n) = 0$ when n is even and $\xi(n) = 1$ when n is odd. Let $a^2b^2 + 4ab \neq 0$. Note that $\alpha + \beta = ab$, $\alpha - \beta = \sqrt{a^2b^2 + 4ab}$ and $\alpha\beta = -ab$. For some properties of these sequences, we refer to [2, 7, 1, 6], and for more general cases of these sequences see [3] and [4].

In this paper, we consider sums of certain products of bi-periodic Fibonacci and Lucas numbers. In particular, we give a general sum formula for the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers that generalize the following results:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_k q_{k+1} = \frac{1}{b} [q_{2n+1}^2 - 1], \tag{6}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{\xi(k)} q_k q_{k+2} = \frac{1}{b} [q_{2n+1} q_{2n+2} - a], \tag{7}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_k q_{k+3} = \frac{1}{b} [q_{2n+1} q_{2n+3} - (ab + 1)]. \tag{8}$$

Yayenie [7, Theorem 6] gave these results as a generalization of Rao’s results in [5], and also he noted that result (8) provides a new result for the classical Fibonacci numbers by the reason of lack of reference. Motivated by results (6)-(8), here we obtain a more general sum formula for the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers. Also, we state an analogous result for the bi-periodic Lucas numbers, and we express the sum of the products of bi-periodic Lucas numbers in terms of the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers. Moreover, we give additional identities for the sums of the form $\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_{k+r}$ and $\sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_{k+r}$, where r is a nonnegative integer.

2. Main Results

First, we start with giving a general sum formula for the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers. Assume that r is a nonnegative integer.

Theorem 1. *For $n > 0$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{\xi(k)\xi(r+1)} q_k q_{k+r} = \frac{1}{b} [q_{2n+1} q_{2n+r} - q_r]. \tag{9}$$

Proof. Assume that r is even. By using the Binet formula (4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} q_k q_{k+r} &= \frac{a^{\xi(k+1)+\xi(k+r+1)}}{(ab)^{\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor + \lfloor \frac{k+r}{2} \rfloor}} \left(\frac{\alpha^{2k+r} + \beta^{2k+r} - (\alpha\beta)^k (\alpha^r + \beta^r)}{(\alpha - \beta)^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{a^{1+\xi(k+1)} b^{1-\xi(k+1)}}{(ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \left(\alpha^r \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^k + \beta^r \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^k - (-1)^k (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} &\sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{a}{b} \right)^{\xi(k)\xi(r+1)} q_k q_{k+r} \\ &= \frac{a^2}{(ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\alpha^r \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^k + \beta^r \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^k - (-1)^k (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \right) \\ &= \frac{a^2}{(ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \left(\alpha^r \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^k + \beta^r \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^k - (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \sum_{k=1}^{2n} (-1)^k \right) \\ &= \frac{a^2}{(ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \left(\frac{\alpha^{r+1}}{ab} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^{2n} - 1 \right] + \frac{\beta^{r+1}}{ab} \left[\left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^{2n} - 1 \right] \right) \\ &= \frac{a}{b (ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \left(\frac{\alpha^{4n+r+1} + \beta^{4n+r+1}}{(ab)^{2n}} - (\alpha^{r+1} + \beta^{r+1}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &q_{2n+1} q_{2n+r} - q_r \\ &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \left(\frac{\alpha^{4n+r+1} + \beta^{4n+r+1} - (\alpha\beta)^{2n} (\alpha\beta^r + \beta\alpha^r)}{(ab)^{2n}} - (\alpha - \beta) (\alpha^r - \beta^r) \right) \\ &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{\frac{r}{2}} (\alpha - \beta)^2} \left(\frac{\alpha^{4n+r+1} + \beta^{4n+r+1}}{(ab)^{2n}} - (\alpha^{r+1} + \beta^{r+1}) \right), \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof for even r . Similarly, it can be proven for odd r . □

Note that for $r = 1, 2$ and 3 we obtain results (6), (7), and (8) respectively.

By using Theorem 1 and the d’Ocagne’s identity

$$q_{2n+1} q_{2n+r} - q_r = \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^{\xi(r)} q_{2n+r+1} q_{2n}$$

in [2, Theorem 5], we can easily obtain the following result.

Corollary 1. For $n > 0$, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{a}{b}\right)^{\xi(k)\xi(r+1)} q_k q_{k+r} = \frac{1}{a^{\xi(r)} b^{\xi(r+1)}} [q_{2n+r+1} q_{2n}]. \tag{10}$$

Now, we give an analogous result for the bi-periodic Lucas numbers.

Theorem 2. For $n > 0$, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^{\xi(k)\xi(r+1)} p_k p_{k+r} = \frac{1}{a^{\xi(r+1)} b^{\xi(r)}} [p_{2n} p_{2n+r+1} - 2p_{r+1}]. \tag{11}$$

Proof. Here, we prove the theorem for the case of odd r . It can be proven similarly for the case of even r . By using the Binet formula (5), we get

$$\begin{aligned} p_k p_{k+r} &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{k+\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\alpha^{2k+r} + \beta^{2k+r} + (-1)^k (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \right) \\ &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\alpha^r \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab}\right)^k + \beta^r \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab}\right)^k + (-1)^k (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_k p_{k+r} &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{\frac{r+1}{2}}} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\alpha^r \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab}\right)^k + \beta^r \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab}\right)^k + (-1)^k (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \right) \\ &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\alpha^r \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab}\right)^k + \beta^r \sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab}\right)^k + (\alpha^r + \beta^r) \sum_{k=1}^{2n} (-1)^k \right) \\ &= \frac{a}{(ab)^{\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\frac{\alpha^{r+1}}{ab} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab}\right)^{2n} - 1 \right] + \frac{\beta^{r+1}}{ab} \left[\left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab}\right)^{2n} - 1 \right] \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{b(ab)^{\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\frac{\alpha^{4n+r+1} + \beta^{4n+r+1}}{(ab)^{2n}} - (\alpha^{r+1} + \beta^{r+1}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &p_{2n} p_{2n+r+1} - 2p_{r+1} \\ &= \frac{1}{(ab)^{2n+\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\alpha^{4n+r+1} + \beta^{4n+r+1} + (ab)^{2n} (\alpha^{r+1} + \beta^{r+1}) - 2(ab)^{2n} (\alpha^{r+1} + \beta^{r+1}) \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{(ab)^{\frac{r+1}{2}}} \left(\frac{\alpha^{4n+r+1} + \beta^{4n+r+1}}{(ab)^{2n}} - (\alpha^{r+1} + \beta^{r+1}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_k p_{k+r} = \frac{1}{b} (p_{2n} p_{2n+r+1} - 2p_{r+1})$$

which proves the desired result. □

In the following corollary, we can easily express the general sum formula for the bi-periodic Lucas numbers in terms of the products of bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers by using Theorem 2 and the identity

$$p_{2n}p_{2n+r+1} - 2p_{r+1} = \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^{\xi(r)} (ab + 4) q_{2n+r+1}q_{2n}$$

in [1, Corollary 3].

Corollary 2. *For $n > 0$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} \left(\frac{b}{a}\right)^{\xi(k)\xi(r+1)} p_k p_{k+r} = \frac{ab + 4}{a} [q_{2n+r+1}q_{2n}]. \tag{12}$$

2.1. The Case of $r = 1$

We express the sum formula (11) in terms of the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers in a simple way. First, consider

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_k q_{k+1} &= q_1 q_2 + q_2 q_3 + q_3 q_4 + q_4 q_5 + \cdots + q_{2n-1} q_{2n} + q_{2n} q_{2n+1} \\ &= q_2 (q_1 + q_3) + q_4 (q_3 + q_5) + \cdots + q_{2n} (q_{2n-1} + q_{2n+1}). \end{aligned}$$

By using the identity $q_{n-1} + q_{n+1} = p_n$ in [1, Theorem 3], we get

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_k q_{k+1} = p_2 q_2 + p_4 q_4 + \cdots + p_{2n} q_{2n} = \sum_{k=1}^n p_{2k} q_{2k}$$

and from (6), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=1}^n p_{2k} q_{2k} = \frac{1}{b} [q_{2n+1}^2 - 1].$$

Similarly, if we consider

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_k p_{k+1} &= p_1 p_2 + p_2 p_3 + p_3 p_4 + p_4 p_5 + \cdots + p_{2n-1} p_{2n} + p_{2n} p_{2n+1} \\ &= p_2 (p_1 + p_3) + p_4 (p_3 + p_5) + \cdots + p_{2n} (p_{2n-1} + p_{2n+1}) \end{aligned}$$

and use the identity $p_{n-1} + p_{n+1} = (ab + 4) q_n$ in [1, Theorem 3], we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_k p_{k+1} &= (ab + 4) [p_2 q_2 + p_4 q_4 + \cdots + p_{2n} q_{2n}] \\ &= (ab + 4) \sum_{k=1}^n p_{2k} q_{2k}. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, we obtain

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_k p_{k+1} = \frac{ab+4}{b} [q_{2n+1}^2 - 1]. \tag{13}$$

Note that this result can also be obtained by using Corollary 2.

Also, we can express formulas (10) and (12) as a product of the bi-periodic Fibonacci and Lucas numbers. By using the identity $q_{2n} = q_n p_n$ in [1, Corollary 5], we can easily get the results

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_k q_{k+1} = \frac{1}{a} [p_n p_{n+1} q_n q_{n+1}] \tag{14}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_k p_{k+1} = \frac{ab+4}{a} [p_n p_{n+1} q_n q_{n+1}]. \tag{15}$$

3. Another Sum Formula for Bi-periodic Fibonacci and Lucas Numbers

In this section, we present an additional theorem for the sums of the form $\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_{k+r}$ and $\sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_{k+r}$, where r is a nonnegative integer.

Theorem 3. *For $n > 0$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_{k+r} = \frac{1}{b} \left(q_{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)+1} - q_{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor+1} \right) + \frac{1}{a} \left(q_{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r+1}{2} \rfloor)} - q_{2\lfloor \frac{r+1}{2} \rfloor} \right), \tag{16}$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{2n} p_{k+r} = \frac{1}{a} \left(p_{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)+1} - p_{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor+1} \right) + \frac{1}{b} \left(p_{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r+1}{2} \rfloor)} - p_{2\lfloor \frac{r+1}{2} \rfloor} \right). \tag{17}$$

Proof. By using the Binet formula of the bi-periodic Fibonacci numbers, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{2n} q_{k+r} &= \sum_{k=1}^n q_{2(k+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)+1} + \sum_{k=1}^n q_{2(k+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor)+1} \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{a}{(ab)^{k+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor}} \left(\frac{\alpha^{2(k+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)} - \beta^{2(k+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)}}{\alpha - \beta} \right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{(ab)^{k+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor}} \left(\frac{\alpha^{2(k+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor)+1} - \beta^{2(k+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor)+1}}{\alpha - \beta} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\alpha - \beta} \left(\alpha \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^{k+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor} - \beta \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^{k+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{a}{\alpha - \beta} \left(\frac{\alpha^{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1}}{(ab)^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1}} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^n - 1 \right) - \frac{\beta^{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1}}{(ab)^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1}} \left(\left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^n - 1 \right) \right) \\
 &+ \frac{1}{\alpha - \beta} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^{\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 1} \left(\left(\frac{\alpha^2}{ab} \right)^n - 1 \right) - \left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^{\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 1} \left(\left(\frac{\beta^2}{ab} \right)^n - 1 \right) \right) \\
 &= a \frac{\alpha^{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)+1} - \beta^{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)+1} - (ab)^n \left(\alpha^{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1} - \beta^{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1} \right)}{(ab)^{n+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1} (\alpha - \beta)} \\
 &+ \frac{\alpha^{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor)+1} - \beta^{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor)+1} - (ab)^n \left(\alpha^{2\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 1} - \beta^{2\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 1} \right)}{(ab)^{n+\lfloor \frac{r-1}{2} \rfloor + 1} (\alpha - \beta)} \\
 &= \frac{1}{b} \left(q_{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor)+1} - q_{2\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor+1} \right) + \frac{1}{a} \left(q_{2(n+\lfloor \frac{r+1}{2} \rfloor)} - q_{2\lfloor \frac{r+1}{2} \rfloor} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

The result for the bi-periodic Lucas numbers can be proven similarly. □

Acknowledgement. We thank the referee for helpful suggestions and comments.

References

[1] G. Bilgici, Two generalizations of Lucas sequence, *Appl. Math. Comput.* **245** (2014), 526–538.
 [2] M. Edson and O. Yayenie, A new generalization of Fibonacci sequences and extended Binet’s Formula, *Integers* **9** (2009), 639-654 .
 [3] M. Edson, S. Lewis, and O. Yayenie, The k-Periodic Fibonacci Sequence and an Extended Binet’s Formula, *Integers* **11** (2011), 739–751.
 [4] D. Panario, M. Sahin, and Q. Wang, A family of Fibonacci-like conditional sequences, *Integers* **13** (2013), (A78).
 [5] K.S. Rao, Some properties of Fibonacci numbers, *Amer. Math. Monthly* **60** (10) (1953), 680–684.
 [6] E. Tan and A.B. Ekin, Bi-Periodic Incomplete Lucas Sequences, *Ars Combinatoria* **123** (2015), 371-380.
 [7] O. Yayenie, A note on generalized Fibonacci sequence, *Appl. Math. Comput.* **217** (2011), 5603-5611.